

Plasma steroid profiling in patients with adrenal incidentaloma

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Contents	Page
Supplemental Methods.....	2
Inclusions according to Study Center and Protocol.....	2
Supplemental table 1.....	2
Patient Follow-up.....	2
Normalizations for Discriminant Analyses	4
Supplemental table 2.....	4
Supplemental Results.....	5
Supplemental table 3.....	5
Logistic Regression	6
Supplemental table 4.....	6
Supplemental figure 1.....	7
References.....	8

Supplemental Methods

Inclusions according to Study Center and Protocol

Inclusion of patients into this retrospective cross-sectional diagnostic study required imaging findings of an incidentally discovered abdominal mass according to entry criteria of one of three clinical protocols in place and approved by local Ethics committees at seven European centers: 1. University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus Dresden, Dresden, Germany; 2. University Hospital of Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany; 3. Institute of Cardiology, Warsaw, Poland; 4. University Hospital of Munich, Munich, Germany; 5. University Hospital of Zürich, Zurich Switzerland; 6. Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, the Netherlands; 7. University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein, Lübeck, Germany (Supplemental table 1).

Supplemental table 1. Numbers of patients included in the analysis according to study center and clinical protocol, before and after exclusions

	DR	WU	WW	MU	ZH	NI	LU
Numbers of patients initially included according to study protocol							
PMT	95	127	130	78	0	10	4
ENSAT	87	8	0	0	0	0	0
PROSALDO	55	3	0	0	17	0	0
TOTAL	237	138	130	78	17	10	4
Numbers of patients included according to study protocol after exclusions							
PMT	91	111	123	73	0	10	4
ENSAT	84	8	0	0	0	0	0
PROSALDO	54	3	0	0	16	0	0
TOTAL	229	122	123	73	16	10	4

Abbreviations: DR, Dresden; WU, Würzburg; WW, Warsaw; MU, Munich; ZH, Zurich; NI, Nijmegen; LU, Lübeck; PMT, Prospective Monoamine Producing Tumor study; ENSAT, European Network for the Study of Adrenal Tumors registry and biobanking protocol; PROSALDO, PROspective study on the diagnostic value of Steroid profiling in primary ALDOsteronism.

Patient Follow-up

Follow-up of patients included by way of the Prospective Monoamine Tumor (PMT) study initially followed the procedures outlined in the primary manuscript that arose from that study (1). However, that study, which was initiated in January 2011, was directed to diagnosis of pheochromocytoma and paraganglioma (PPGL). Thus, initial follow-up focused on identification of previously undiagnosed patients with PPGL and exclusion of PPGL in other patients. Nevertheless, exclusion of disease in patients with an incidentaloma was based in most patients on an alternative diagnosis (e.g., non-functional adenoma, adrenocortical carcinoma, aldosterone- or cortisol-producing adenoma) established after resection of the mass or based on routine laboratory tests employed to establish an alternative diagnosis. In other patients exclusion of PPGL was based on negative results of repeat biochemical testing at follow-up, including in some patients negative results of confirmatory testing according to the clonidine suppression test. Imaging characteristics, such as unenhanced attenuation Hounsfield unit (HU) values on computed tomography (CT), also provided evidence to exclude a PPGL in isolated patients. Among the patients with incidentaloma included via the PMT study, an alternative diagnosis was thereby initially reached in 241 patients by January 2018.

Further follow-up of patients without a diagnosis of PPGL, who were enrolled into the PMT study, was initiated in January 2020. This involved comprehensive review of patient records within hospital information systems at Munich, Würzburg and Dresden by a single investigator (KB). Two other investigators searched and reviewed medical for patients enrolled into the PMT study at Warsaw (AK) and Nijmegen (JWML). This second follow-up of patients enrolled into the PMT study was

aimed at confirming, refining or correcting initial diagnoses and included establishing a diagnosis in those patients in whom PPGL was excluded on the basis of negative biochemical testing for PPGL. That second follow-up was completed in April 2021 and was then further supplemented by a final check of patient classifications by study investigators at each of the aforementioned centers, which was completed at the end May 2021. Through this process, among the 444 patients with incidentaloma included via the PMT study a final diagnosis was reached in 437 patients. However, among those 437 patients a further 25 patients were excluded from the study on the basis of measurable plasma concentrations of dexamethasone or due to findings that the incidentally discovered mass had an extra-adrenal location.

Importantly, among the patients with a corrected diagnosis on follow-up there was one 45-yr old male patient with a 1.4x1.5 cm right adrenal mass discovered incidentally by CT in 2010. That patient was included into the PMT study in May 2016 at which time the adrenal mass remained stable in size on imaging. The patient did not have hypertension and apart from reporting periods of nausea was otherwise asymptomatic. Biochemical testing indicated a plasma concentration of normetanephrine of 102 pg/mL (0.56 nmol/L), which was under the upper cut-off of age specific reference intervals (148 pg/mL, 0.81 nmol/L), and a plasma concentration of metanephrine of 93 pg/mL (0.47 nmol/L) that was just above the upper cut-off of reference intervals (88 pg/mL, 0.45 nmol/L). With follow-up under the PMT protocol, PPGL was excluded on the basis of imaging characteristics that suggested an adenoma. In November 2020 the patient was referred back to the endocrine outpatient clinic because of development of palpitations, tremor and hyperhidrosis. Plasma concentrations of metanephrine were increased to 166 pg/mL (0.84 nmol/L) and CT revealed a slightly enlarged adrenal mass (1.8x1.5 cm) with CT unenhanced attenuation HU values of 20. A mass measuring 2.2 cm was resected in February 2021 and pathologically confirmed to be a pheochromocytoma.

For the 75 patients with adrenal incidentaloma initially included by way of the PROSpective study on the diagnostic value of steroid profiling in primary ALDOsteronism (PROSALDO) trial, the focus of that study was on confirmation and exclusion of primary aldosteronism. Among the 26 patients with PA that were included into the analysis by way of this protocol, that diagnosis was ultimately based on final confirmation by a saline infusion test (SIT) that required both plasma aldosterone concentrations above (58 ng/L) 162 pmol/L by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LCMS/MS) and above 61 ng/L (170 pmol/L) by routine immunoassay measurements. Exclusion of PA was based on negative results for LC-MS/MS measurements for the SIT, which when positive by immunoassay had to be confirmed to be negative by an independent LC-MS/MS method. In this way PA was excluded in 49 patients. Among these 49 patients, a plasma concentration of cortisol above 1.8 µg/dL (50 nmol/L) after the dexamethasone suppression test (DST) was used to define autonomous cortisol secretion (ACS) in 14 patients. Pheochromocytoma was excluded based on negative biochemical test results for measurements of plasma free metanephrines and/or an alternative diagnosis. For two patients a final diagnosis under PROSALDO could not be reached and these patients were excluded from the final study population. The remaining patients with a negative DST were defined to have non-functional adrenal incidentaloma (NFAI).

The remaining 95 patients from Dresden and Würzburg were included into the study by way of the European Network for the Study of Adrenal Tumors (ENSAT) registry and biobanking protocol. These patients were enrolled into that protocol between April 2013 and May 2021. Diagnosis of adrenocortical carcinoma (ACC), ACS, NFAI, PA or pheochromocytoma was based on established routine diagnostic procedures supplemented by review of medical records undertaken at Dresden by three investigators (K.B., G.C., J.M.) and at Würzburg by one investigator (O.K.). Three patients were excluded, two based on lack of sufficient information for a diagnosis and the other based on diagnosis of an ACTH-secreting adrenal pheochromocytoma.

Normalizations for Discriminant Analyses

Plasma concentrations of many adrenal steroids show marked differences according to sex and age, including lowered concentrations with advanced age (2). For some steroids, such as corticosterone and DHEA, upper cut-offs of reference intervals are between 2.5- and 9.7-fold higher in 25 compared to 75 year olds and vary according to sex. In the present series of patients with incidentaloma, although age for half of all patients was between 50 and 67 years, the range varied widely from 17 to 86 years and necessitated consideration in models. However, rather than using age-specific reference intervals for normalization we chose to use the geometric means of age-related distributions (supplemental table 2). These were calculated similarly to age and sex-specific reference intervals described in the original report and using the data from the reference population and according to the curve-fitting procedures described in that report (1). For aldosterone and cortisol, where influences of age were significant but relatively small, linear models were used for correction based on regression equations. Similarly, linear models were used for calculating age-specific mean concentrations of normetanephrine according to large populations of patients described elsewhere and where the data are also available in excel datasets of the supplement (3). For analytes that showed no or negligible relationships with age (i.e., 18-oxocortisol, 18-hydroxycortisol and metanephrine), sex-specific geometric mean concentrations were calculated. Age and sex specific geometric means were then used as denominators to normalize plasma concentrations of analytes, with a further base 10 logarithmic transformation applied before discriminant analyses.

Supplemental table 2. Factors for normalization of plasma concentrations of selected analytes for influences of age and sex.

Analytes	Males	Females
Steroids (ng/mL)		
Aldosterone	$-0.000468 \times \text{age} + 0.07587$	$-0.001079 \times \text{age} + 0.11737$
18-Oxocortisol*	0.0128	0.0128
18-Hydroxycortisol*	0.8489	0.5956
11-Deoxycorticosterone	$0.33046 \times 10^{-0.0081356 \times \text{age} - 0.669511}$	$0.33046 \times 10^{-0.0096353 \times \text{age} - 0.673573}$
Corticosterone	$14.83 \times \text{age}^{-0.522}$	$92.6 \times \text{age}^{-0.8867} - 081928$
11-Deoxycortisol	$0.34646 \times 10^{-0.0018946 \times \text{age} - 0.187305}$	$0.34646 \times 10^{-0.0025784 \times \text{age} - 0.310487}$
Cortisol	$-0.72786 \times \text{age} + 141.01$	$-1.2210547 \times \text{age} + 156.74$
17-Hydroxyprogesterone†	$2.502 \times \text{age}^{-0.3158}$	0.750 / 0.224
Androstenedione	$-0.2887 \times \text{age}^{-0.2771} + 1.7814$	$2.2552 \times e^{[-0.02023 \times \text{age}]}$
DHEA	$11.868 \times e^{[-0.03028 \times \text{age}]}$	$8.2805 \times e^{[-0.02637 \times \text{age}]}$
DHEA-Sulfate	$0.3685 \times 10^{-0.0077304 \times \text{age} + 4.0167611}$	$0.3685 \times 10^{-0.0051228 \times \text{age} + 3.7204205}$
Catecholamine O-methylated metabolites (pg/mL)		
Normetanephrine	$0.54895 \times \text{age} + 43.09$	$0.54895 \times \text{age} + 43.09$
Metanephrine*	33.9	25.7

*For 18-oxocortisol, 18-hydroxycortisol and metanephrine, impacts of age were not significant or minimal and normalizations were based on mean concentrations of the reference population. † for 17-hydroxyprogesterone there is a pronounced impact of menopause on distributions of this steroid and normalizations were based on mean concentrations for females before and after the age of 50.

Supplemental results

Supplemental table 3. Plasma concentrations of 16 adrenal steroids and metanephrines among the 577 patients with adrenal incidentaloma

	ACC	ACS	NFAI	PA	PHEO
N	19	104	312	65	77
Aldosterone (ng/L)	36 [18-61]	36 [19-64]	42 [22-76]	156 [83-313]***	44 [22-70]
18-Oxocortisol (ng/L)	16 [10-42]	13 [6-26]	13 [5-28]	73 [31-324]***	10 [5-23]
18-Hydroxycortisol (ng/mL)	0.71 [0.391-0.96]	0.71 [0.45-0.94]	0.63 [0.44-0.94]	1.17 [0.71-2.577]**	0.52 [0.32-0.76]*†
18-Hydroxycorticosterone (ng/mL)	0.31 [0.20-1.46]§	0.43 [0.20-0.77]	0.42 [0.29-0.60]	0.83 [0.40-1.61]*†	0.52 [0.37-0.92]*
11-Deoxycorticosterone (ng/L)	108 [61-243]**	50 [29-75]*	36 [24-56]	51 [33-103]*	41 [23-65]
Corticosterone (ng/mL)	2.10 [1.01-4.05]	1.95 [1.10-3.66]	1.94 [1.23-3.62]	1.97 [1.34-3.29]	2.48 [1.20-3.99]
11-Deoxycortisol (ng/mL)	2.92 [0.51-9.68]**	0.38 [0.25-0.58]*	0.26 [0.16-0.40]	0.29 [0.19-0.47]	0.26 [0.15-0.46]†
Cortisol (ng/mL)	117 [79-184]	123 [93-153]	119 [92-150]	106 [83-131]	134 [96-170]§
Cortisone (ng/mL)	17.7 [14.2-22.9]	19.2 [15.5-22.6]	19.4 [16.0-22.4]	18.3 [14.0-21.6]	19.8 [16.9-23.5]
11-Dehydrocorticosterone (ng/mL)	0.59 [0.40-0.80]*	0.81 [0.45-1.03]*	0.94 [0.67-1.32]	0.80 [0.54-1.18]	1.26 [0.91-1.74]*†¶
21-Deoxycortisol (ng/L)	11 [2-41]	17 [9-33]	19 [9-39]	24 [12-49]	20 [9-33]
Progesterone (ng/L)	180 [83-265]**	35 [17-84]	39 [19-89]	52 [26-106]	45 [20-71]
17-Hydroxyprogesterone (ng/mL)	1.01 [0.60-2.48]**	0.44 [0.22-0.77]	0.46 [0.21-0.79]	0.44 [0.24-0.73]	0.42 [0.21-0.72]
Androstenedione (ng/mL)	1.07 [0.76-2.30]**	0.43 [0.30-0.74]	0.56 [0.37-0.83]	0.61 [0.49-0.91]†	0.60 [0.46-0.83]†
DHEA (ng/mL)	2.33 [1.19-5.13]	1.24 [0.71-2.13]*	1.74 [1.07-3.35]	2.58 [1.48-4.53]†	2.73 [1.51-3.97]†
DHEAS (ng/mL)	1739 [734-2637]*	393 [212-648]****	655 [341-1220]	867 [494-1482]	929 [506-1505]
Normetanephrine (ng/L)	91 [57-105]†	92 [67-128]	79 [64-111]	71 [48-96]	627 [276-1882]***
Metanephrine (ng/L)	27 [17-32]	31 [21-45]	28 [18-41]	27 [21-42]	170 [40-482]***

Plasma concentrations are shown in ng/mL or ng/L. ***P<0.001, **<0.02 higher than all groups;****P<0.0001 lower than all groups; *P<0.02 different from NFAI; †P<0.01 different from ACS; §P<0.05 different from PA; ¶P<0.02 different from ACC. Table excludes data for testosterone, dihydrotestosterone and methoxytyramine. For conversion of ng/mL to nmol/mL or ng/L to nmol/L divide by molecular weight (Supplemental table 4).

Logistic Regression

Logistic regression analysis using nine steroids (11-deoxycortisol, 18-oxocortisol, androstenedione, 18-hydroxycortisol, corticosterone, DHEAS, cortisol, 17-hydroxyprogesterone and aldosterone) that were selected based on stepwise variable selection and construction of receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves indicated best discrimination for the steroid panel alone was for patients with PA versus all others (Supplemental figure 1). The area under the ROC curve, with 95% confidence intervals (CIs), for discrimination of patients with PA from all other patients was 0.931 [0.893-0.956] and was not significantly increased by inclusion in models of measurements of plasma metanephrines or plasma metanephrines and adrenal mass size (panel D). Next best discrimination using the steroid panel along was observed for patients with ACC (panel A) where the AUC was 0.910 [0.793-0.964]. Although the AUC increased to 0.977 [0.897-0.955], this increase failed to reach significance ($P=0.0574$) according to 95% CIs of the difference in AUCs [-0.001-0.0779].

Supplemental table 4. Formulae and molecular weights (MW) of the 19 adrenal steroids measured by LC-MS/MS

Analytes	Formula	MW
Steroids		
Aldosterone	$C_{21}H_{28}O_5$	360.44
18-Oxocortisol	$C_{21}H_{28}O_6$	376.45
18-Hydroxycortisol	$C_{21}H_{30}O_6$	378.46
18-Hydroxycorticosterone	$C_{21}H_{30}O_5$	362.46
11-Deoxycorticosterone	$C_{21}H_{30}O_3$	330.46
Corticosterone	$C_{21}H_{30}O_4$	346.46
11-Deoxycortisol	$C_{21}H_{30}O_4$	346.46
Cortisol	$C_{21}H_{30}O_5$	362.46
Cortisone	$C_{21}H_{28}O_5$	360.44
11-Dehydrocorticosterone	$C_{21}H_{28}O_4$	344.46
21-Deoxycortisol	$C_{21}H_{30}O_4$	346.46
Progesterone	$C_{21}H_{30}O_2$	314.46
17-Hydroxyprogesterone	$C_{21}H_{30}O_3$	330.46
Androstenedione	$C_{19}H_{26}O_2$	286.41
DHEA	$C_{19}H_{28}O_2$	288.42
DHEA-Sulfate	$C_{19}H_{28}O_5S$	368.49
Testosterone	$C_{19}H_{28}O_2$	288.42
Dihydrotestosterone	$C_{19}H_{30}O_2$	290.44
Dexamethasone	$C_{22}H_{29}FO_5$	392.46
Catecholamine O-methylated metabolites		
Normetanephrine	$C_9H_{13}NO_3$	183.20
Metanephrine	$C_{10}H_{15}NO_3$	197.23
Methoxytyramine	$C_9H_{13}NO_2$	167.21

increase in the AUC to 0.773 [0.725-0.814] and 95% CIs of the difference in AUCs [0.006-0.041]. Again thereafter, addition of tumor size to the model had negligible influence on diagnostic performance.

AUCs for steroid panels used alone were 0.751 [0.700-0.797], 0.732 [0.674-0.785] and 0.652 [0.605-0.696] for the respective identification of patients with ACS (panel B), pheochromocytoma (panel E) and NFAI (panel C) among all other groups. As expected, addition of plasma metanephrines to models considerably improved ($P<0.0001$) identification of patients with pheochromocytoma according to an AUC of 0.993 [0.928-0.997] and 95% CIs of the difference in AUCs [0.205-0.317]. The AUC was little affected thereafter by additional inclusion of tumor size to the model (panel E). Addition of plasma metanephrines to models also considerably improved ($P<0.0001$) diagnostic performance for identification of patients with NFAI compared to all others (panel C) according to an AUC of 0.808 [0.769-0.841] and 95% CIs of the difference in AUCs [0.115-0.197]. Thereafter, addition of tumor size to the model had negligible influence on diagnostic performance.

Addition of plasma metanephrines to the models resulted in a small but significant improvement ($P=0.0100$) also for discrimination of patients with ACS from all other groups (panel B), as indicated by an

Supplemental figure 1. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for use of the steroid profile alone (SP) or combined with plasma metanephrines (SP/M) or both plasma metanephrines and adrenal mass size (S) for discrimination of patients with ACC, ASC, NFAI, PA and pheochromocytoma (PHEO) from all four other groups combined. AUC = areas under ROC curves.

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